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EFFECTS OF EMPLOYEES' UPWARD FEEDBACK IN CREATING NEW OPPORTUNITIES TO STRENGTHEN JOB PERFORMANCE

Wickramasinghe, G.L.D.^a and Wickramasinghe, V.^b

^a Department of Textile and Clothing Technology, Faculty of Engineering, University of Moratuwa, Moratuwa, Sri Lanka. e-mail: dharmasri@uom.lk

^b Department of Management of Technology, Faculty of Engineering, University of Moratuwa, Moratuwa, Sri Lanka. e-mail: vathsala@uom.lk

ABSTRACT

Since the phase-out of the Multi-Fibre Agreement, the worldwide system of managed trade in apparel exports through the quota system, export-apparel manufacturers had to rethink their operations management strategies for survival and growth. One of such strategies adopted to improve the efficiency of apparel production is lean manufacturing. Lean manufacturing system relies heavily on employees' capabilities for its effective implementation. Shop-floor employees play a key role in the process of minimisation of waste in the lean production context since they interact with the direct operational environment. They have more ownership of the production process and have capacity to make better improvement suggestions. Based on a sample of lean manufacturing system implemented manufacturing firms in Sri Lanka, the study investigated relationships between upward feedback, job performance and the age of lean manufacturing system. It was found that the age of the lean manufacturing system moderates the positive relationship between upward feedback and job performance in such a way that longer the lean manufacturing system is in operation, higher will be its positive effect on the relationship between upward feedback and job performance.

Key Words: upward feedback, job performance, lean manufacturing, lean duration, age of the lean manufacturing system.

INTRODUCTION

Importance of feedback is well emphasised in the literature (Bauer and Mulder, 2006). The literature identifies that receiving and providing feedback is important for both employees and supervisors, and constructive feedback leads to create learning oriented organisational climate. The majority of research studies investigated the importance of providing constructive feedback to employees by their supervisors (Bauer and Mulder, 2006). However, it is equally important to consider situations where employees could provide constructive feedback to their supervisors and the effects of such feedback on employees themselves (Bauer and Mulder, 2006). The feedback provided by employees to their supervisors is known as “upward feedback”, which is the focus of this paper.

The present study is conducted in the export-apparel manufacturing firms that implemented lean manufacturing systems. The recent developments occurred in the export-apparel manufacturing sector imply the importance of effective implementation of lean manufacturing systems.

In brief, the export-apparel manufacturing industry in Sri Lanka witnessed a remarkable growth since late 1970s and has emerged as the country's leading export manufacturing industry. This growth is mainly due to the introduction of Multi-Fibre Agreement (MFA), the worldwide system of managed trade in apparel exports through the quota system in 1974. During the regime of the MFA, export-apparel manufacturers in Sri Lanka had enjoyed a relatively assured export

market through bilateral agreements with the developed world based on the quota system. Since the total phase-out of MFA quota system in the year 2005, other competitive dimensions such as productivity and quality, therefore, have taken centre stage. This change of priorities has influenced export-apparel firms to rethink their operations management strategies for survival and growth. Since the mid-2000s, export-apparel manufacturers in Sri Lanka identified possibilities for them to turn to lean manufacturing systems for improving the efficiency of production systems.

Lean manufacturing centres on the elimination of waste (Womack et al., 1990). Waste in the context of lean manufacturing is diverse including overproduction, waiting times, unnecessary movement of materials, inappropriate processing, inventory, defects, underutilization of people, environmental waste, and underutilization of facilities (Kollberg et al., 2007; Womack and Jones, 1996; Vinodh et al., 2011). In the process of minimisation of waste, shop-floor employees play a key role since they interact with the “direct” work environment (Losonci et al., 2011). Undoubtedly, they are more knowledgeable of what is happening in the factory, and lean manufacturing system has a considerable effect on their day-to-day task accomplishment (Losonci et al., 2011). Therefore, when export-apparel firms capturing and capitalising on employees' capabilities, there is a need to better understand shop-floor employees' reactions to work organization in the lean manufacturing system.

In this context, the objectives of the study are to investigate:

- 1) effect of shop-floor employees' upward feedback on their job performance, and
- 2) whether "for how long the lean manufacturing system is in operation" or the age of the lean manufacturing system (termed as "lean duration" in this study) moderates the relationship between upward feedback and job performance.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In lean manufacturing environment, shop-floor employees' involvement in decision making is very high (Womack and Jones, 1996; Womack et al., 1990). They are expected to make a contribution towards the improvement of the production system (Womack and Jones, 1996; Womack et al., 1990). Further, supervisors should show true interest in worker involvement to push them in this direction (Forza, 1996). On the one hand, shop-floor employees have more ownership of the process, and have the capacity to make better improvement suggestions (Forza, 1996). On the other hand, the solution of problems by shop-floor employees places more power on them (Wilkinson. and Oliver, 1989; Forza, 1996) and provides them with a sense of achievement in lean efforts (Lucey et al., 2004).

Specifically, in lean manufacturing, shop-floor employees are in a more self-managed factory than in a command-and-control factory (Womack et al., 1990). They are given cross-training to be capable of operating multiple machines, performing quality control activities, solving quality problems using their multi-skills to reduce work-in-progress, idle equipment, and indirect staff involvement (Forza, 1996). Hence, in some situations shop-floor

employees are more knowledgeable of operations than that of their supervisors. Further, shop-floor employees have more opportunities to participate in decision making than conventional factory. According to Forza (1996) "opportunities of meetings with managers and technicians are frequent in a system in which the exchange of information, both informal through frequent and direct communication, and formal in occasions such as continuous improvement groups, team briefings and quality circles are considered to be very important" (p.47). Therefore, feedback from shop-floor employees on continuous improvement provides others with a means of learning. Therefore, upward feedback has positive effects on both shop-floor employees and their supervisors. From the side of supervisors, this upward feedback provides them with opportunities for learning while from the side of shop-floor employees, upward feedback provides them with a feeling of co-determination at the workplace (Bauer and Mulder, 2006).

When considering the benefits for shop-floor employees in detail, upward feedback creates positive feelings in shop-floor employees since they perceive upward feedback as a possibility of influence and improvement (Bauer and Mulder, 2006). For instance, Bauer and Mulder (2006) found that employees who perceive upward feedback as a chance of improving their working conditions also perceive more autonomy, competence and social relatedness at the workplace. Further, Steinhoff (1995) found that subordinates perceive upward feedback make them equal partners in the communication process, which give them opportunities to influence existing practices, and ultimately increase their job

satisfaction and work motivation. Specifically, in the lean manufacturing context, upward feedback can create positive effects on co-operation and team building, which are vital for social integration processes in the lean manufacturing environment.

However, the majority of research studies on feedback concentrated on how feedback received could contribute to develop a learning-oriented climate in organisations from feedback receivers' perspective (e.g. Kinicki et al., 2004; deShon et al., 2004). Few studies have investigated how feedback provision could contribute feedback provider. Such studies provide evidence that provision of feedback impacts on feedback provider by enhancing his/her intrinsic motivation (Deci et al., 1994; Ilgen et al., 1979). For instance, research studies of Deci et al. (1994) and Ilgen et al. (1979) found feedback provision creates feeling of competence in feedback provider. However, these studies were not conducted in operations management or business management context. Therefore, empirical studies are needed to investigate the beneficial effects of upward feedback on feedback provider.

In the present study we argue that shop-floor employees' upward feedback creates positive feelings in them and leads to increase their job performance. Therefore, the research question of this contribution is whether upward feedback contributes to higher levels of shop-floor employees' job performance since they perceive upward feedback as a possibility of influence and improvement. Further, in our study we argue that it is difficult to create a participative work environment overnight since such environments naturally demands

changes to the social organization that requires some time to receive acceptance from both shop-floor employees and their supervisors. Therefore, in this present study we propose that "for how long the lean production is in operation" (lean duration) will moderate the relationship between shop-floor employees' upward feedback and their job performance. Therefore, it is hypothesized:

H1: Upward feedback will positively influence job performance of shop-floor employees.

H2: Lean duration will positively moderate the relationship between upward feedback and job performance.

Research model is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Research Model

METHOD

Sample and Method of Data Collection

The target population for the study is a cross-section of shop-floor employees engaged full-time in export-apparel manufacturing firms, which have implemented a formal lean manufacturing system in the whole manufacturing function and where lean manufacturing has become the standard of operation for at least one year in Sri Lanka. Authors of this paper identified 12 export-apparel manufacturing firms that had

implemented lean manufacturing systems and running for at least one year. These 12 firms were considered as the population frame for this study and all the firms agreed to participate in the survey. Self-administered survey questionnaire was distributed among the firms covering at least 5 per cent of the total shop-floor employees in each firm, and 420 usable responses were received.

Measures

Upward feedback was assessed by 8-items from Bauer and Mulder (2006). This scale evaluated employees' satisfaction with the form of feedback, whether it is perceived as a possibility to share critical opinions, whether it leads to real changes in the perception of the subordinates, and whether it is acknowledged by the supervisors (Bauer and Mulder, 2006, p. 514).

Work performance implicitly means doing better or worse than comparable other (Price, 1997). Generally, self-report measures of individual performance were considered more appropriate because the individual is uniquely aware of the elements of high performance when the focus is on the perspective of the individual worker (Rodwell et al., 1998). Work performance was measured by four items from self-rating scale developed by Rodwell et al. (1998).

Data on the age of the lean manufacturing system or lean duration were measured in years.

Method of Data Analysis

Structural equation model (SEM) was developed using AMOS 16. Fit measures relating to absolute fit (CMIN/df, GFI), relative fit (CFI), parsimonious fit (PRATIO), and fit measures based on the non-central chi-

square distribution (RMSEA, PCLOSE) were used to evaluate the model-data fit.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 summarises the results of SEM. In the preliminary stages of data analysis, the variables of age, gender, the highest level of education, and tenure were entered as controls. Due to highly homogeneous nature of shop-floor employees in the export-apparel industry, none of these variables were significant. In the process of purifying the SEM model, these controls were removed.

Table 2 shows the fit measures for the model. The model well satisfies the requirements of goodness-of-fit criteria (see Byrne 2001).

A graph was created by plotting two-way interaction effects to depict the moderating effect of lean duration on the relationship between upward feedback and job performance. Figure 2 shows this graph.

Table 1: Summarised results of SEM

Relationship	Regression Estimate	S.E.
Job performance <--- Lean duration	.654***	.036
Job performance <--- Upward feedback x Lean Duration	.750***	.009
Job performance <--- Upward Feedback	.649***	.056
UF 1 <--- Upward Feedback	.653***	.062
UF 2 <--- Upward Feedback	.646***	.063
UF 3 <--- Upward Feedback	.717***	.062
UF 4 <--- Upward Feedback	.744***	.069
UF 5 <--- Upward Feedback	.660***	.063
UF 6 <--- Upward Feedback	.746***	.067

Relationship	Regression Estimate	S.E.
UF 7 <--- Upward Feedback	.750***	.066
UF 8 <--- Upward Feedback	.648***	.043
JP 1 <-- Job performance	.557***	.089
JP 2 <-- Job performance	.661***	.139
JP 3 <-- Job performance	.503***	.121
JP 4 <-- Job performance	.607***	.118

UF=Upward feedback measures, JP= Job performance measures.

Table 2 : Model-data Fit Summary

CMIN/DF	GIF	RMSEA	PCLOSE	CFI	PRATIO
4.844	.853	.056	.880	.892	.897

Figure 2: Moderating effect of lean duration on the relationship between upward feedback and Job performance

The data shown in Table 1 and Figure 2 suggest that longer lean duration strengthens the positive relationship between upward feedback and Job performance.

Overall, H1 predicted that upward feedback will positively influence job

performance of employees. The data shown in Table 1 support H1. H2 predicted that lean duration will moderate the positive relationship between upward feedback and job performance in such a way that longer the lean duration, higher will be the positive effect of lean duration on the relationship between upward feedback and job performance. The data shown in Table 1 and Figure 2 support H2.

CONCLUSION AND MANAGERIAL IMPLICATIONS

The findings of the study provide a new dimension of feedback from shop-floor employees to their supervisors, which untimely increase shop-floor employees' job performance. In other words, feedback provision helps to increase feedback providers' job performance.

The findings imply that feedback provision helps to increase recognition of shop-floor employees in the organisation, which in turn increases their self-esteem and satisfaction. However, it is also possible to assume that upward feedback will be effective in an organisational climate which maintains trust among organisational members (supervisors and subordinates) and encourages such feedback from shop-floor employees.

However, it is also implied that implementing lean manufacturing concepts in the factory demands changes to the social system of work. Further, such changes cannot be made in the factory overnight and it will take some time to accept such changes by both shop-floor employees and their supervisors. Hence, the lean duration or "for how long lean manufacturing system is in operation" can become a major criteria that moderate the relationship between upward feedback and job performance.

This study was limited to investigate the effects of upward feedback on employees' job performance. Future research could investigate the effects of upward feedback on supervisors' job performance.

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